

JAMAL KAMAL’S TRANSLATION OF SHAKESPEARE’S WORKS

Odilova Mavluda To‘lqinjon qizi

Master’s degree student of FerSU

mavludaodilova22@gmail.com

Yusupova Sabohatxon A’zamjonovna

Senior teacher, English language department of FerSU

s.a.yusupova@pf.fdu.uz

Annotation: This article describes Jamal Kamal's translation of Shakespeare's works, the general difficulties of translating English literature, and the wider introduction of Shakespeare's works to the Uzbek readership.

Key words: literary feature, journalistic work, historical work, literary criticism, neologism, sonnet, translation studies.

Translation enriches the spiritual life of a person, the potential possibilities of language makes it come true, gives it a gloss. A book to translate in this regard the choice offering is also of great importance. The function of literature is influenced by periods it is a task, as it consists of creating works that are not subject to change it also applies to translation. Re-translation of a previously translated work after doing Shakespeare is not only a person's unique individuality, but also a person sought to give unchanging, immortal properties in its nature. Hamlet, Othello, Macbeth, King Lear is the property of Eternity, not to change with the passage of periods are works designed to stay. Translation of Shakespeare's works into Uzbek-grammar of the Uzbek language, increases lexical, stylistic capabilities, socio - Artistic of Uzbek literature serves to increasingly strengthen the position.

Indeed, the Uzbek language of Shakespeare's works was reborn into the fact that this language the beginning of life in a cultural and contemplative environment is a great achievement for the Uzbek people. Uzbekistan opens a wide way to Shakespeare and continues the traditions of Shakespeare to the ranks of countries that were able to show their talent and creative potential added. To see the influence of Shakespeare's genius in the work of a huge number of Uzbek writers can. These are Oybek, G.Gulam, H.Alimjan, M.Sheikhzade, harmonious, T.To la and others. Shakespeare's influence on the work of Uzbek writers, first of all, historical found expression in addressing topics. Resurrect the past of our people, coverage of his pages, imbued with the spirit of progressive, national liberation, to serve the time of history, as Shakespeare's song says in its interpretation in order to refer to history in literature. Implementation of materials from Shakespeare's works in Uzbek literature practical was possible. To be more precise, the English playwright of the 16th century

almost all that appears in his work as an artistic reality XIV the century took place in Central Asia as real historical events. Of this in the literature reflected example M. It was the tragedy of sheikhzade “Mirzo Ulugbek”.

The purpose of the creation of this tragedy, undoubtedly, suddenly appeared in Sheikhzade not only, or the result of Shakespeare's translation of the tragedy “Hamlet” not born. This is a thorough study of Shakespeare's work in a broad sense, making it a new implementation in accordance with the requirements of period literature, based on new materials which consist of development. And M.Sheikhzade, in turn, skillfully this is the best of the tasks. Just as the development did not stop, the development of literature continues it is enough. Shakespeare's works are a number of translators (Chulpan, M.Sheikhzadeh, G'.Ghulam, S.Even after the translation by Ahmad), their new, it was felt the need for more perfect, closer translations to the original. In Particular, C.When Kemal talks about the creation of the translation of the tragedy” Hamlet” it should be noted that the arbibi of our national theater is a scientist Khodjev J.Towards Kamal as long as he called and asked to turn over the tragedy “Hamlet” again. Chulpan translation prose using a Russian-language intermediary, M.And Sheikhzadeh translated his own since the Russian and Azerbaijani language intermediary is carried out on the basis of translations, now J.Kamal was required to turn the translation from the original text. The scientist Boshayev if the translation ride out without means from the original, then the work is on the stage jarangi believed that it would be special. People's poet of Uzbekistan, full of 12 dramas and sonnets of Shakespeare a hardworking translator who has paid his translation to our people J.Kamal's own translations for the first time in our literature made it on the basis of the original. Without knowing the original, it I known for its meaning, expression, music, color representation and figurative charm talking about translation without imagination in the sense did not see, did not understand it's like testifying to something, says himself. The tragedies “Hamlet” and “Macbeth”, translated by Kamal, are comparative from the analysis therefore we can witness that these translations are artistic, philosophical, ideological, educational, aesthetic directions in full and adequate embodied. These translations of Shakespeare's works are new in our cultural-literary life, an important phenomenon, which undoubtedly took a worthy place in the treasury of Uzbek literature; an impetus to the development of translation work was given. Currently, our people's passion for reading foreign works of literature it is high and has the tools and activities in our literature translators cannot meet this requirement fully. For this reason in our country the development and support of the translation industry is of urgent importance. The skills of translators who grew up in the bosom of our literature like Kamal and the experience, the legacy of their creation in our literature is a kind of translation the basis for the school of slogan. The creators of the future

generation also studied at this school they add their valuable masterpieces to the treasury of our literature, of course.

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